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journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jasrepTechnologies of tradition: A compositional and technological characterisation of pottery production at Late Bronze Age Enkomi, Cyprus[☆]Chase Alan Mohan Minos^{a,*}, Maria Dikomitou-Eliadou^a, Elvira Vassilieva^b, Patrick Degryse^b^a Science and Technology of Archaeology and Culture Research Centre, The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus^b Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

The Late Bronze Age in Cyprus (c. 1680/1650–1050 BCE) marked significant economic, political, and social transformation, evident in new settlement patterns, urbanisation, craft specialisation, and growing ties with the Eastern Mediterranean. Enkomi, located on Cyprus' eastern coast, exemplifies these developments, evolving into a major urbanised settlement during the Late Cypriot Bronze Age. Despite extensive excavations, much of the site's early history remains underexplored (c. 1680/50–1350 BCE), with limited research addressing the formative phases of this significant settlement.

This study builds on prior research by conducting a comprehensive technological and compositional analysis of ceramics from Enkomi's early phases, focusing on what are perceived as locally produced wares (Plain White, Red/Black Slip, and White Painted Wheel-Made). By combining macroscopic, petrographic, and geochemical analyses, this study uncovers long-standing clay preparation traditions. The findings offer a refined understanding of local production choices, revealing that potters adhered to shared technological practices despite chronological, stylistic and technological changes. This research fills a critical gap by establishing a robust baseline for identifying local ceramic production at Enkomi and its local traditions, enabling more accurate future interpretations of ceramic production organisation, commodity circulation, and cultural exchange as well as technological evolution in Cyprus during the LBA.

1. Introduction¹

The Late Bronze Age (LBA; c. 1680/1650–1050 BCE) on the island of Cyprus witnessed a gradual increase in economic, political and social complexity (Crewe, 2007a: 7–8; Knapp 2013; 2024). This development was marked by growing connections with the rest of the Eastern Mediterranean, alongside new settlement patterns, changes in spatial organisation, craft specialisation, urbanisation, burial practices and the adoption and development of new technologies, such as the potter's wheel (Negbi, 1986: 97–98; Keswani, 2004; Knapp, 2013: 348–350; Crewe, 2007a; Crewe and Georgiou, 2018). Many of the material changes, which culminated around the 'urban climax' of the Late Cypriot IIC (c. 1300 BCE), reflect the emergence of an increasing off-island predisposition that was preceded by a preferential relocation, or reorganisation (Webb, 2018: 23) of settlements to previously uninhabited, coastal parts of the island (Webb and Knapp, 2021: 232–233), including

sites such as Palaepaphos, *Kalavastos-Ayios Dhimitrios*, Maroni-Vournes, Hala Sultan Tekke, and Enkomi.

Located on the eastern coast of Cyprus, ancient Enkomi was one of these new sites that, over the course of the Late Cypriot period (hereafter LC), developed into a large, urbanised settlement (Crewe, 2007a). Despite several excavations in the late 19th and 20th centuries, the Late Bronze Age (hereafter LBA) settlement was not systematically excavated until the joint excavations by a French mission led by Claude Schaeffer (1952) and the Cyprus Department of Antiquities, directed by Porphyrios Dikaïos (1969–71). Since then, Enkomi has remained central to scholarly debate as a pivotal site for the study of Late Bronze Age on the island and, importantly, the only one to exhibit 'extensive exposure of the earliest occupation' of the LC periods (LCI-IIB, c. 1650–1325 BCE; Crewe, 2007a: 158).

Enkomi has been argued to be a preeminent site on the island for copper production, the control of its internal distribution (e.g., through

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fortresses along the rivers, Fortin, 1981), and its export. The LBA economy of many of these new coastal sites likely depended significantly on this industry, as well as on the commodity extraction and circulation systems that were in operation (Knapp, 2013: 406–407; Kassianidou, 2013: 144; Crewe, 2007a: 65; Merrillees, 1971). Enkomi is also strongly associated with the ‘state-like’ entity of ‘Alašiya’, mentioned in the Amarna letters and other Bronze Age texts (Holmes, 1971; Knapp, 2024: 74–76). However, evidence for Enkomi as a potentially powerful, authoritative and urban settlement dates from the LCIIIC period. Before this time (LCI-IIB), Enkomi was more likely organised into a more modest, discrete way, and most likely did not exert authority over the rest of the island (Crewe, 2007a: 75, 159–160).

Presenting a more balanced and nuanced view of Enkomi in LCI-IIB, Crewe (2007a; 2008) re-examined, quantified, and re-dated the ceramic evidence from the excavations of Dikaios (1969–1971). The scholar also addressed the complex adoption of a new technology, the potter’s wheel (Crewe and Knappett, 2012; Crewe, 2007b). Based on her typological, macroscopic and statistical analysis, Crewe (2015: 126) observed that, in terms of fabrics (macroscopically identified), the same potters were producing both decorated wares such as Red or Black Slip and undecorated wares like Plain White.

Complimenting her research, the petrographic and bulk chemical compositional analysis presented in this paper, not only supports the visual, macroscopic similarity in the fabrics that Crewe noted, but also reveals that clay recipes were part of a shared tradition over the course of the LCI-IIB periods, around 300–350 years. In fact, based on current evidence and preliminary findings from another study in progress by the authors, the clay recipes in use in the early LBA at Enkomi appear to continue into the Iron Age (IA) in nearby Salamis, forming what seems to be a long-standing tradition, characteristic of the eastern coast of Cyprus.

Therefore, this paper aims to address this gap in research and hopes to serve as a reference for future studies on other early LC sites. It presents a comprehensive technological and compositional investigation, examining the choices made by local potters at or near Enkomi for the production of wares found at the site, i.e. Plain White Handmade and Wheel-made (hereafter PWHM/WM), Red and Black Slip (hereafter R/BSHM, R/BSWM), and White Painted Wheel-made Ware II (hereafter WPWMII).

1.1. Previous research on LBA Cypriot ceramics

Pottery analysis from Bronze Age Cyprus has significantly advanced in recent decades, particularly through the integration of elemental and isotopic techniques alongside petrographic analysis. There have been several cross-regional ceramic studies focusing on single ceramic classes, such as White Slip (e.g., Courtois and Velde, 1981; Gomez et al., 1995; Gomez and Doherty, 2000; Cordivari and Boileau, 2024), Base Ring (e.g., King, 1987; Vaughan, 1991), Red Lustrous Wheel-made (Knappett et al., 2005; Kibaroglu et al., 2025), Plain White (e.g., Tschegg et al., 2009a), Plain White Wheel-made (e.g., Tschegg et al., 2009b), cooking pots (e.g., Dikomitou-Eliadou et al., 2016), and pithoi (e.g., Xenophontos et al., 2000; Pilides, 2000: 111). There have been also comparative and inter-regional studies of different wares (e.g., Artzy, 1976; Jones, 1986; Bryan, et al., 1997; Renson et al., 2013a; Renson et al., 2013b; Grave et al., 2014; Mountjoy and Mommsen, 2015; Åström, 1972) that have contributed to our understanding of compositional and technological variation within and among ceramic wares, and within and among regions, providing a broader understanding of technological choices, technological evolution, and cultural exchange. Analytical studies of Cypriot ceramics move beyond the island to include LBA Cypriot imports in other parts of the eastern Mediterranean, including Anatolia (e.g., Haciosmanoğlu et al., 2018), Crete (e.g., Tomlinson et al., 2010), the Levant (e.g., Artzy et al., 1973), and Egypt (e.g., Merrillees, 1968).

Research has primarily concentrated on finer and more elaborately

decorated pottery types, their composition and provenance, with fewer cases focusing on the local production at key sites, such as Alassa (Nodarou, 2017; Jacobs and Borgers, 2015; Jacobs et al. 2015; Renson et al., 2013a), Pyla-Kokkinokremnos (Porta and Cannavò, 2024) and Hala Sultan Tekke (Renson et al., 2011; Renson et al., 2014; Waiman-Barak et al., 2023), where more localised studies have been conducted. The compositional and technological characterisation of local ceramic production and consequently the identification of the production profile of a settlement or a region is pivotal, as this provides a baseline understanding of the preferred materials, techniques, know-how, and traditions within a given area. It ensures that subsequent regional or interregional comparisons are grounded in accurate knowledge of what is local and non-local at each site. Without this foundational knowledge, broader analyses risk misinterpreting the significance of pottery circulation, trade, exchange, and cultural interactions, as they would lack the clarity provided by the distinct compositional and technological characteristics of local ceramic production (Rice, 1987: 315; Arnold et al., 1991).

1.2. Overview of earlier analyses of LBA pottery from Enkomi

At Enkomi, the situation is comparable in that analyses have been sporadically conducted over the last century on a wide variety of wares and contexts spanning the LBA. However, none have exhaustively or diachronically sampled local, undecorated pottery from early LC contexts. An earlier compositional study of pottery from the Bronze Age Aegean in the mid-1960s included samples from Cyprus (n = 11 from Enkomi) but their focus was on Mycenaean ‘Pictorial pottery’ (Catling and Millet, 1965). Later, Catling et al. (1978) began to shift their attention to wares such as PW, comprehending that these wares were distinct from their Aegean counterparts due to their elevated, but variable chromium (Cr) content (Jones, 1986: 326). They noted that PW, in particular, was difficult to classify, indicating the use of multiple clay sources.

The compositional profile of Enkomi established thus far by Jones (1986), who compiled numerous studies on the island, is characterised by the use of ‘coarse clays’ containing transported and weathered ophiolitic rock fragments. The clays are consequentially heterogeneous, and lack uniformity in specific element concentrations, especially Cr (Jones, 1986: 342–344). Jones (1986: 343) further stated that the analytical data, especially petrographic evidence, supports the likelihood that potters exploited multiple sources, using them individually or mixing them depending on the vessel type.

Despite the large number of samples selected from Enkomi, especially for NAA, the overwhelming majority are later (post-LCIIC) ‘Mycenaean’ wares, imitations of Mycenaean pottery, or fine handmade wares. Comparatively, few samples represent PW, R/BS or WPWMII wares. Anson (1980a and 1980b) analysed only three sherds of PW among 88 LCIII Rude Style vessels, attempting to correlate typology with geochemistry. However, the primary focus was on the origin of Rude Style in Cyprus (Cherry and Knapp, 1994: 70). Anson (1980a) also sampled six clay deposits around the site of Enkomi, reporting that they closely matched the Rude Style vases, but not PW. Similarly focusing on later LCIII pottery, Mountjoy and Mommsen’s (2015) study using NAA identified an Enkomi group (‘CypI’) as the largest within their total Cypriot ceramic database. They attributed the vessels to a workshop located either at or close to Enkomi; a conclusion further supported by clay samples analysed by Artzy (1976). However, to date, no evidence of a workshop has been found at Enkomi (Crewe, 2007b: 216), apart from a few misfired vessels discovered in tombs (Schaeffer, 1936: 75–78, 135, Tombe 3, no. 5; Keswani, 1991: 111), and some possible potting discs (with ambiguous functionality) identified by Crewe in Area III (Crewe, 2007a: 148).

There is, therefore, an established understanding of the composition of ceramics produced after LCIIIB (1350 BCE). The development of ceramic production at Enkomi until this point is primarily supported by

Crewe's important typological and statistical study, but from a petrographic and bulk geochemical perspective, the data remain scarce. More recently, [Tscheegg et al. \(2009a\)](#) conducted analyses on PW samples from Enkomi, using material from Dikaios's excavations. While their research shared related interests, it primarily focused on provenience and did not sample a diachronic or exhaustive number of PW specimens. The only other study on non-fine material from Enkomi is [Ioannides et al. \(2024\)](#), although this work focuses on technical and metallurgical ceramics.

2. Materials and sampling strategy

The 95 ceramic sherds selected for sampling derive from the 1948–1958 excavations of Porphyrios Dikaios (1969–1971) in Areas I and III, and include only material identified as stratigraphically and chronologically secure by [Crewe \(2007a: 90–91\)](#). In total, approximately 19,600 sherds were examined, though this represents only a portion of the material excavated at Enkomi by Dikaios, not to mention that recovered by [Schaeffer \(1952\)](#). Therefore, the dataset is considered here as already constituting a targeted population ([Drennan, 2009: 93](#)).

Nearly all of the contexts are composed of secondary refuse or redeposited fill used for floor levelling ([Crewe, 2007a: 89](#)), meaning the material was deposited away from its original place of use ([Schiffer, 1972: 161](#)). Samples were taken from a variety of rooms, where sufficient diagnostic material was available (Supplementary Material 1: Sample List; see [Crewe, 2007a](#) for drawings of key shapes). The deposits derive from the Area III 'fortress', a location of significant copper-working activity in the later history of the site ([Crewe, 2007a: 86](#); [Ioannides et al., 2024](#)), and Area I, which is more closely associated with elite domestic activity ([Crewe, 2007a: 105](#)).

The samples were distributed as proportionately as possible across the chronological periods, wares, and shapes ([Crewe, 2007a: 74](#)). Therefore, of the total ceramic assemblage, approximately 30% are PW, 20% are R/B Slip, and 9% are WPWMII ([Crewe, 2007a: 90–91](#); [Fig. 1](#)). R/BS and WPWMII wares are typically jugs, with a 99% occurrence rate ([Crewe, 2007a: 99](#)). PW is only marginally more variable, containing over 90% closed medium sized vessels in terms of wheel-made vessels, and more rarely large jars and small bowls ([Crewe, 2007a: 102–103](#)). PWHM is slightly more diverse with most vessels (c. 70%) being large or very large closed vessels ([Crewe, 2007a: 102](#)). A proportionate number

of each ware was sampled for analysis, based on the fine phasing levels established by Crewe (PW n = 53, R/BS n = 36, and WPWMII n = 6; see [Fig. 2](#)). These samples were selected for their similarities in fabric and their likely local origin ([Crewe, 2007a: 101](#)). In addition, six PW pithoi were included in the analysis, not only because they are believed to be of local origin but also due to the suggestion that their manufacture involved itinerant potters.

When considering the manufacturing techniques, R/BS shows a steady transition from handmade to wheelmaking techniques, before the ware eventually ceases to be produced at the end of LCIB ([Crewe, 2007a: 101](#)). In contrast, PW was predominantly produced on the wheel throughout the LCI-IIB periods, although its shape variety decreased over time ([Crewe, 2007a: 106](#)). As its name suggests, WPWMII was exclusively produced using wheelmaking techniques and was largely confined to the LCIB period.

3. Geological setting in eastern Cyprus

The site of Enkomi is situated approximately 6–8 m above sea level, and 3 km from the present coastline (EU-DEM E60N10, [Copernicus Land Monitoring Service](#)). It is located within the eastern part of the Mesaoria Plain. The Mesaoria Plain features sheetwash colluvium, deltaic sediments, and ancient river gravels, composed of a mix of clasts derived from the Troodos Ophiolite Complex and the Circum-Troodos Sedimentary Succession, with a layer of recent alluvial deposits covering them ([Cohen et al., 2012: 253](#)). It has been argued that the Mesaoria plain soils have high clay contents ([Cohen et al., 2012: 253–254](#)). The site of Enkomi is surrounded by alluvial and colluvial deposits, including sediments from the Nicosia and Athalassa formations ([Fig. 3](#), also [Geological Survey Department, Cyprus \[GSD\] 1995](#)). The Pedaios and Gialias Rivers, the two longest rivers on the island, converge just south of Enkomi. These rivers transport weathered material derived from ophiolitic, mafic, and ultramafic rocks of the Troodos Mountains. The sedimentary formations within the watershed surrounding Enkomi are predominantly composed of calcareous marls from the Nicosia Formation, which include biocalcarenes, marls, limestones, and sands. The area is also influenced by sediments from the Athalassa Formation, which are characterised by similar lithologies ([GSD, 1995](#)). These are the raw material deposits within a 7 km radius of Enkomi ([Fig. 3](#)) –

Fig. 1. Percentage of wares across levels (fine phases) in Areas I and III at Enkomi, after [Crewe \(2007a: Fig. 17.3\)](#). For correlation of fine and coarse phases with chronological periods, see [Crewe, 2007a: 73–74](#) and [Fig. 11.3](#). Note that these fine phases do not correspond to the fine phases of LC, but rather to the Levels defined in Dikaios' excavation.

Fig. 2. Number of samples taken by chronology and ware from Enkomi.

Fig. 3. Geological map of the area around Enkomi. Geological data courtesy of the Geological Survey Department.

identified by Arnold (1993: 68) as the maximum threshold distance for pottery-making communities cross-culturally to source raw materials, though it can vary depending on specific ecological and cultural factors. Moreover, evidence suggest the likely presence of an inland bay or lagoon in the area during the LBA, when Enkomi was occupied (Devillers, 2008). This palaeogeographic feature could have influenced the selection and availability of raw materials used by potters at the time.

4. Methodology

The overarching framework of this research employs the *chaîne opératoire* approach (Lemonnier, 1986; Dobres, 1999; Roux, 2017) to

systematically analyse the stages of pottery production, illuminating the technological choices and cultural decisions made by the potters at each stage (Gosselain, 2018). This interdisciplinary approach enables a detailed examination of raw material selection and preparation during the LCI-II periods at Enkomi, at a pivotal time when new technological practices, such as the potter’s wheel and related techniques for wheel-made and wheel-thrown pottery, were introduced into later stages of production.

Ceramic petrography was the primary method of analysis (n = 95), employing a systematic protocol to describe microstructures, groundmass, and the distribution and texture of inclusions within the ceramic thin sections (Whitbread, 1986; 1995; Quinn, 2022). Frequency categories for descriptions were estimated following a system proposed by

Fig. 4. Petrographic groups at Enkomi by chronology.

Quinn (2022: 108) and Whitbread (1995: 379). Frequency categories and estimations for inclusions were made using visual area charts (as in Quinn, 2022: 100) and frequency labels (Quinn, 2022: 108; Whitbread, 1995: 379). The full descriptions and frequency labels for inclusions, as presented in Supplementary Material 3, are therefore semi-quantitative, as neither point counting nor digital image analysis methods were employed to quantify inclusion frequencies. All thin sections were made at the Archaeological Science laboratories of STARC at the Cyprus Institute, and they were studied using a Zeiss Axiolab 5 polarising microscope.

A Hitachi XMet 8000 handheld X-ray fluorescence analyser (hhXRF) was used to identify preliminary compositional groupings among the Enkomi wares. Measurements were taken on off-cuts from thin-section preparation after sufficient drying. Using the Hitachi's mining and soil mode calibrations, three spots per sherd were measured for 120 s in each mode. Standard reference materials (SARM69 and NIST2711a) were measured before and after each session, achieving precision and accuracy below 15%, except for V, Cu, and Ni.

A subset of samples ($n = 33$) was analysed at KU Leuven using ICP-MS and ICP-OES to quantify major, minor, and trace elements. The samples were selected based on initial petrographic groupings and identified to be local. With this more precise and accurate method of analysis, the aim was to establish the bulk elemental composition of the local sherds. As noted below, three sherds turned out to be petrographic outliers and were excluded from further statistical processing of the elemental data.

Major and minor elements were determined by OES (Varian 720ES), while trace elements were determined by MS (Agilent 7700x). Preparation of the ceramic samples followed a lithium fusion method described in Keleşhi et al. (2024). Nine certified reference materials (SPS-SW2 1/10, SO-1, SO-2, GBW-7311, GBW-7411, CCH-1, GFS-401, GBW-7114, NIST-2710) and several internal standards were analysed to ensure the precision and accuracy of the instruments, which were approximated and calculated as described by Keleşhi et al. (2024).

For the ICP-MS, precision was generally below 5%, with exceptions of As, Hf, Ta and Zr; for the OES, precision was mostly below 5% with the exception of ZrO (~15%). Accuracy of the ICP-MS, with the exception of elements with very low concentrations near to the detection limit, was less than 10% but some were higher (Be, Hf, La, Sc, Ta and Tl)

and subsequently were excluded from statistical analyses. Accuracy of the ICP-OES was less than 5% with the exception of ZnO (~12%), P₂O₅ (~27%), CuO (~32%), and ZrO (~9%). Cu was in any case immediately excluded due to the likely post-depositional contamination of the ceramics in copper working areas of Area III, which was also supported by SEM-EDS. Variable transformations, univariate and multivariate statistics for all elemental data were processed using the statistical packages in IBM's SPSS (v.26).

Selected sherds were prepared as polished blocks and analysed using a Zeiss EVO 15 scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) and the Oxford Instruments Aztec programme. This analysis aimed to assess relative firing temperatures based on the degree of vitrification of clay particles in calcareous pastes, following established criteria (Maniatis and Tite, 1981).

5. Results

5.1. Ceramic petrography: Fabric groups and technology

Of the 95 samples under study, three general fabric² groups (hereafter Groups) were identified. Group A is the largest, (Fig. 4), representing 74% of the total sample set and comprising six subgroups. Groups B and C are much smaller, containing only 8 and 6 samples, respectively (see Supplementary Material 1 for the full list of samples by group (including subgroups), and Supplementary Material 3 for the complete petrographic descriptions).

Some general observations can be made about the local Groups as a whole. The sorting of inclusions remains relatively consistent across Group A's subgroups. Also, the geological origin of the mineral inclusions in Groups B and C is the same as that of Group A. The matrix is consistent across all groups, ranging from red to yellow-brown (50x, XPL), when lower fired, and green to grey-brown, when higher fired (also macroscopically green [5Y 5/6], Crewe, 2007a: 235). Matrices are generally calcareous, containing fine calcite and varying proportions of carbonate inclusions. A core is very rare in all groups. Overall, Group A

² In the context of this work, the term *fabric* is used as defined by Whitbread (1995: 368).

Fig. 5. Subgroup A1A: a) ENK51 (BS jug) and b) ENK75 (WPWMII jug). Photomicrographs in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm. Note the area in photomicrograph (a) of ENK51, where inclusions are less frequent – a characteristic feature of this subgroup.

can be described as a medium to fine sand tempered fabric rich in both carbonate and ophiolitic inclusions. Subgroups A1-A3 are presented below.

Group A has a higher and lower fired subgroup as well as two finer subgroups and one more rich in serpentinite. Group B is a fine fabric with random large carbonate and ophiolitic inclusions that are open spaced. Group C is a very fine fabric also with random carbonate and ophiolitic inclusions but its subgroup C1B has only sedimentary derived inclusions.

5.2. Group A: Moderately calcareous fabric with medium to fine sand, including quartz, carbonates, and ophiolitic inclusions

5.2.1. Subgroup A1A

Chronology: LCIA: 5, LCIB: 7, LCIB-IIA: 4, LCIA-B: 11.

Wares: RBSWM: 8, RBSHM: 3, PWWM: 10, PWHM: 4, WPWMII: 2.

Subgroup A1A is the primary and most populous fabric subgroup ($n = 27$, Fig. 5a-b). The carbonate inclusions are often in varying stages of

decomposition, with only rare instances of complete microfossil decomposition observed. The matrix ranges from active to moderately inactive, with both zones present within individual thin sections. Voids typically constitute around 10% of the fabric and are primarily vesicular, frequently associated with microfossils. Planar voids and channels are rare but, when present, are often aligned parallel or diagonal to the vessel walls.

The density, distribution, and frequency of inclusions in this subgroup exhibit some variation, though not significant enough to justify the formation of further meaningful subgroups. Inclusions are generally between 0.1 and 0.35 mm, with rare larger inclusions measuring approximately 0.5–0.6 mm. Frequent inclusions include angular to subangular monocrystalline quartz, rounded to subangular micritic limestone, as well as rounded microfossils. Basalt is frequent to common, while subangular to angular clinopyroxenes, subrounded serpentinite, chert, and opaques are common but vary in proportion.

Finally, textural concentration features (TCFs) are common to few, and argillaceous rock fragments (ARFs) are few to very few (Fig. 5a).

Fig. 6. Subgroup A1B: a) ENK3 (BS jug) and b) ENK42 (PWWM bowl). Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

Fig. 7. SEM photo in secondary electron mode showing the vitrification of clay particles in subgroup A1B sample ENK11 (BS jug). Magnification: 1500x, scale bar: 10 µm.

Epidote, olivine, plagioclase, polycrystalline quartz, and quartzite are very few to rare, but are consistently present in nearly all samples in comparable proportions. Overall, the fabric exhibits weak bimodality, though this is based on simple observations rather than digital image or grain size analysis, neither of which were possible in the scope of this research. This observation is likewise evident in the other subgroups (A1B-A3). Combined with the coarse grain size of the inclusions (>0.1 mm), the even distribution of larger inclusions throughout the matrix, as well as, in some cases, the presence of TCFs – resulting from added material appearing as clumps – it is argued that this fabric was tempered with medium-to-fine or very fine, likely alluvial, sand. The fine fraction is composed of quartz, opaques and pyroxenes, and serpentine.

5.2.2. Subgroup A1B (higher fired)

Chronology: LCIA: 5, LCIB: 8, LCIB-IIA: 2, LCIIA-B: 1.

Ware: RBSHM: 4, RBSWM: 5, WPWMI: 3, PWWM: 3, PWHM: 1.

Subgroup A1B (n = 16) is characterised by a green to green-brown (5Y 5/6 macroscopically) matrix that is optically inactive (Fig. 6a-b). All

Fig. 9. SEM photo in secondary electron mode of subgroup A1C sample ENK8 showing partial vitrification. Magnification: 1300x, scale bar: 10 µm.

the carbonate inclusions appear to be fully decomposed, except in a few cases, as in samples ENK39 and ENK68. As a result, voids are primarily micro- to meso-sized and are associated with decomposed carbonates, which are always less than 0.3 mm in size and often have a red reaction ring around them (Fig. 6a). Serpentine is less frequent in this subgroup, but when present, it is always altered, showing orange/red birefringence colours (Braekmans and Degryse, 2017, Table 15.1). In the SEM, this higher firing was also evident from the clear sintering and vitrification of the clay particles (Fig. 7).

5.2.3. Subgroup A1C (lower fired)

Chronology: LCIA: 1, LCIB: 3, LCIB-IIA: 0, LCIIA-B: 3.

Ware: PWWM: 5, PWHM: 1, RBSHM: 1.

Subgroup A1C (n = 7) is the lower fired variant, characterised by an optically active matrix, with no decomposition of microfossils or carbonates, and often containing unaltered serpentine that exhibits green or yellow birefringence colours (Figs. 8a-b and 9). Voids and inclusions are oriented diagonally to the walls of the vessels. However, the matrix around them is not darkened. Altered serpentine is rarer but does co-

Fig. 8. Subgroup A1C: a) ENK8 and b) ENK31, PWWM jars. Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

Fig. 10. Subgroups A2A (left) and A2B (right): a) ENK15 (PWWM jar) and b) ENK64 (RS jug). Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

exist with its unaltered counterpart in ENK8. The variation in subgroups based on firing temperature and the combination of heat-altered and unaltered serpentinite, as well as the infrequent presence of a core, may suggest a weakly controlled firing regime, or limited effort to achieve strong atmospheric control. Evidence of clay mixing is particularly pronounced in this subgroup, especially in samples ENK47 and ENK95, which exhibit a range of textural concentration features, including ovoid forms, in combination with frequent lamination. They are typically red-brown in XPL (50x) and rarely green-brown (ENK47 mostly), concordant and with diffuse borders.

5.2.4. Subgroups A2A and A2B

Chronology: LCIA: 7, LCIB: 2, LCIB-IIA: 3, LCIIA-B: 3.

Wares: RBSHM: 5, RBSWM: 1, PWWM: 6, PWHM: 2, WPWMI: 1.

Subgroups A2A ($n = 11$, Fig. 10a) and A2B ($n = 4$, Fig. 10b) are finer variants of subgroup A1, divided into an optically inactive subgroup (A2A) and an optically active subgroup (A2B). The matrix is relatively dense, with voids not exceeding 10%. These voids are primarily vesicles associated with decomposed carbonates. A2B has more voids (20%), mostly in the form of meso-sized vughs. Inclusions are fewer in both subgroups, and the grain size rarely exceeds 0.25 mm, with very rare cases of inclusions larger than 0.5 mm. Monocrystalline quartz, micritic limestone, and microfossils are frequent. Plagioclase is common, while serpentinite, chert and opaques are few. Basalt, dolerite, calcite, and epidote are very few to rare. TCFs are more common in these subgroups and include lenses, laminae, and some that lack clear, regular shapes.

Fig. 11. Subgroup A4: a) ENK4 and b) ENK87, BS jugs. Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

Fig. 12. Group B: a) ENK 21 (PW pithos or jar) and b) ENK26 (PW pithos). Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

5.2.5. Subgroup A3

Chronology: LCIA: 2, LCIB-IIA: 1, LIIA-B: 2.

Ware: RBSWM: 2, RBSHM: 2, PWWM: 1.

Subgroup A3 (n = 5, Fig. 11a-b) is characterised by a significant increase in the proportion of serpentinite (common). The serpentinite predominantly exhibits orange or red birefringence colours. Basalt and dolerite are very few to rare, while quartz, carbonate and feldspar inclusions are common to frequent. The matrix is moderately active to inactive, with zones of each occurring, and it rarely shows a weakly defined core.

5.3. Group B: Fine fabric with sedimentary, ophiolitic inclusions and monocrystalline quartz

Chronology: LCIA: 6, LCIB: 2.

Ware: PWHM: 3, PWWM: 2, RBSHM: 2, RBSWM:1.

Group B's (Fig. 12a-b) matrix is moderately calcareous, homogeneous, and ranges from inactive to moderately active. It is green to red brown, and yellow-brown in XPL. Voids make up approximately 10% of the matrix and are mostly channels, vesicles or vughs; planar voids are absent. Similarly to Group A, this fabric is dominated by monocrystalline quartz. Polycrystalline quartz is frequent, and plagioclase, carbonates (micritic limestone and microfossils), serpentinite and clinopyroxenes are common to few. Inclusions in the coarse fraction are open-spaced and moderately sorted, with grain sizes ranging from 0.1 to 0.4 mm. The relatively continuous range within the sand fraction, from a few medium to fine sand grains, along with visible silt in the fine fraction, is typical of a natural sediment distribution. The fine fraction is predominantly quartz.

Fig. 13. Subgroups C1A (left) and C1B (right): a) ENK49 (PW pithos) and b) ENK41 (PW pithos). Photomicrographs are in XPL; field of view = 5.6 mm.

5.3.1. Subgroups C1A and C1B: Very fine fabric with large, open-spaced and random sedimentary or ophiolitic inclusions

Chronology: LCIA: 2, LCIB: 3, LCIB-IIA: 1.

Ware: PW Pithos: 6.

Subgroup C1A (n = 5, Fig. 13a) is characterised by a more poorly sorted grain size distribution, ranging from 0.1 to 1.5 mm. The matrix is moderately to low calcareous and is green, red, to yellow–brown in XPL. Voids are approximately 5–10%, varying significantly between samples. Vughs and vesicles are the most common, channels are very rare and planar voids are absent. ENK 27, 49 and 56 contain frequent quartz and sandstone, while ENK28 and 49 have more frequent serpentinite and limestones (micritic and laminated). What unites these samples is the modality, grain size distribution and open-spacing of inclusions, as well as the frequent occurrence of quartz in both the coarse and fine fractions. TCFs are also common in this group, including laminae, a few clay pellets, and some that lack clear, regular shapes. Ophiolitic and metamorphic rock fragments are very rare to absent.

C1B is a small subgroup (n = 1, Fig. 13b) that is more calcareous and contains inclusions of predominantly sedimentary origin. It is dominated by carbonates, such as subrounded to rounded micritic limestone, chert, and microfossils.

5.3.2. Outliers

Chronology: LCIA: 2, LCIB: 6, LCIB-IIA: 1, LCIIA-B: 2.

Wares: PWHM: 3, PWWM: 5, RBSHM: 1, RBSWM: 2.

The outliers, designated with the prefix ‘O’ in Supplementary Material 1, comprise 11 samples. Their full descriptions can be found in Supplementary Material 3. While this paper focuses on the characterisation of the ‘local’ groups at Enkomi, some general observations about the outlier samples are noteworthy, adding to our understanding of compositional variability within the Enkomi pottery assemblage.

Firstly, the relatively small number of outliers within the overall dataset suggests that the sampling strategy employed was largely effective, particularly given the study’s focus on material believed to represent Enkomi’s local ceramic production. Among the 11 identified outliers, eight are PW and only three are R/BS. The finest fabrics are represented by ENK9 (O1) and ENK57 (O8), both PW bowls, which have dominant TCFs and ARFs, respectively. These two samples share a similar frequency of argillaceous inclusions and TCFs; however, they exhibit limited mineralogical similarities that would otherwise support their grouping. ENK14 (O2), a R/BSWM jug is marked by prominent TCFs and large metamorphic rock fragments, significantly larger than those observed in any of the local groups from Enkomi.

ENK35 (O4), a PWWM bowl, displays a heterogeneous matrix with a more frequent occurrence of primary calcite and polycrystalline quartz. ENK50 (O6), a PWWM jar, stands out due to the frequent presence of coarse, sand-sized micritic limestone and medium sand-sized sandstone fragments, components not found in the local Enkomi groups at comparable sizes or frequencies.

ENK66 (O9) is a PWHM jar that is distinguished by the dominant presence of coarse, sand-sized serpentinite inclusions (both altered and unaltered), exhibiting varied textures. ENK79 (O10) is a PWWM jug that contains frequent micritic limestone and argillaceous inclusions, as well as larger chert inclusions.

Four samples (O3: ENK32, O5: ENK43, O7: ENK53, O11: ENK88) particularly stand out due to their distinct fabric characteristics. For example, ENK32, a PWWM bowl, a R/BSHM jug, contains a high concentration of primary calcite and (unaltered) serpentinite inclusions within a grey matrix. ENK43 features large grains of monocryalline quartz (~0.8 mm) and also medium sand-sized fragments of metamorphic rocks, such as quartzite (0.3–0.4 mm), which are notably larger than those observed in Group A. ENK53, a RBSWM jug, also contains large monocryalline quartz grains, reaching up to 1.2 mm in size. ENK88, a PWWM bowl, is characterised by well-sorted and rounded monocryalline quartz and micritic limestone inclusions set in a non-calcareous red matrix. These fabric traits set these four samples apart

from the broader assemblage and suggest different sources of raw material and/or alternative production practices. Although not included in the geochemical results, it is important to note that three (ENK35, ENK43, ENK53) of the 11 outliers were also analysed using ICP-MS/OES, revealing distinct elemental compositions that further justify their divergence from the other samples.

Chronologically, most of the outliers can be attributed to the LCIB period. However, given the small number of examples, it is difficult to argue that this proportion reflects a broader trend of increased imports to Enkomi during the LCIB. Typologically, a notable number of outliers appear to be PW bowls, which may be significant, as PW (whether handmade or wheel-made) bowls tend to be more commonly associated with mortuary contexts (Crewe, 2007a: 132–133). However, the significance of this observation would require a more systematic study on the typological and fabric differences between PW bowls in mortuary versus settlement contexts.

6. Geochemical results

6.1. hhXRF

The hhXRF was used to assess any possible internal variation among the local pottery at Enkomi and the correspondence between petrographic and elemental groupings. Following statistical and graphical analysis of the data, the elemental compositions of the three major fabric groups (Groups A, B and C) are similar, with only minor variation (Table 1). A consistent trend of variability is observed for certain elements, such as Cr, Ni, and MgO, which aligns with previous analyses of these three wares (Jones 1986: 341–343) and is reflected in typological, chronological, or spatial groupings. Ni, Cr, and Fe values appear to be slightly higher on average in the LCIIA-B period (Fig. 14a). It seems unlikely that this reflects a shift towards more igneous raw materials or a source closer to the ophiolite complex. Indeed, apart from nine exceptions, which includes four petrographic outliers, Cr/Ni (ppm) ratios range from 1.6 to 4.4% (Fig. 14a–d). The natural variability of the raw materials, as noted by Jones (1986), seems to be the more likely cause, especially given the site’s location at the confluence of the islands’ two longest rivers. Groups B and C, however, tend to have lower Cr/Ni ratios when compared to Group A, despite lower CaO and higher SiO₂ content.

Post-depositional effects on the bulk chemistry are evident in many samples. Contamination from Cu was identified only in sherds located in copper-working rooms (101, 103, 105) of Area III. The higher fired subgroup A1B shows lower K₂O (%) and Rb (ppm), which may be attributed to leaching of K and Rb in higher fired ceramics (Quinn, 2022: 355; Buxeda i Garrigós et al., 2002). Conversely, the opposite trend is observed in the rest of the samples, particularly in the lower fired subgroup A1C (Fig. 15a–b). Principal component analysis (PCA), performed on log-transformed data (base 10), reveals that variation between fabric groups and wares is minimal when K and Rb are excluded (Fig. 16a–d). Cr was also excluded due to a potential ‘nugget effect’ occurring, which was subsequently observed in the ICP analysis, as discussed below.

6.2. ICP-MS and ICP-OES

A similar trend of stability across time, wares and petrographic groups was largely confirmed by the ICP-MS and ICP-OES analyses despite the smaller sample size – although a recent re-analysis of the thin sections revealed that three samples submitted for geochemical analysis were outliers; two (ENK43 and ENK53) were compositionally distinct from the local ‘Enkomi group’ (Group A), while one (ENK35) had a similar but not identical composition. Post-depositional contamination or geochemical alteration, initially observed with hhXRF, was confirmed by the ICP-MS analyses. For example, sherds found in copper working areas of the site still exhibited elevated Cu values, with some exceeding 1000 ppm. Similarly, variations in the alkali sums, alkali ratios (wt.%) and Rb content (ppm) between the higher-fired (A1B) and

Table 1

Results of the hhXRF by petrographic groups including standard deviations (stdev.), and coefficients of variation (CV%). Note in particular that the mean values for CaO are ~2% lower in Groups B and C, likely reflecting the reduced frequency of carbonate inclusions compared to Group A. Otherwise, the mean values and variation in element concentrations, as expressed by stdev. and CV%, are very similar between groups with the exception of MgO in Group C. The elevated MgO value may reflect either the petrographic characteristics of Group C or the relative inaccuracy of the hhXRF. As no Group C sherd was analysed with ICP-MS or OES, it is difficult to attribute this minor variation to a specific. Source. In contrast, the variation in CaO values can be more confidently explained by the lower frequency of carbonate inclusions observed petrographically, and potentially by greater refinement of the raw materials.

Element	Petro Group A			Petro Group B			Petro Group C		
	Mean	STDEV	CV (%)	Mean	STDEV	CV (%)	Mean	STDEV	CV (%)
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	13.6	0.8	5.5	13.8	1.1	8.2	13.8	0.3	2.3
CaO (%)	16.2	2.4	15.1	14.9	2.3	15.7	14.1	2.2	15.3
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	8.4	1.0	11.9	7.7	0.7	9.0	8.5	0.4	4.7
K ₂ O (%)	1.8	0.3	18.8	2.0	0.3	15.6	2.1	0.1	5.4
MgO (%)	8.6	1.1	12.8	8.8	1.2	14.6	10.0	1.4	14.1
MnO (%)	0.2	0.03	14.6	0.2	0.01	8.3	0.2	0.01	6.6
SiO ₂ (%)	50.7	1.9	3.8	52.0	2.3	4.5	51.0	1.7	3.3
TiO ₂ (%)	0.6	0.1	13.2	0.6	0.07	13.2	0.5	0.03	5.7
Cr (ppm)	582	245.9	42.2	570	86.8	15	563	93.4	17
Ni (ppm)	206	34.4	16.7	223	41.9	19	250	40.3	16
Rb (ppm)	63	14.5	23.0	72	8.2	11	91	5.9	7
Sr (ppm)	680	100.1	14.7	649	103.4	16	601	120.2	20
Ba (ppm)	367	100.6	27.4	323	94.8	29	439	88.9	20

Fig. 14. Biplots of: a) Cr/Ni (ppm) against Fe₂O₃ (wt.%) by chronology; b) Cr/Ni (ppm) against Fe₂O₃ by ware; Cr/Ni (ppm) against Fe₂O₃ by fabric group; and, d) Cr against Ni (ppm) by fabric group (Group).

lower-fired (A1C) petrographic subgroups were most evident when plotting against the LOI% (Table 2 and Fig. 15a-b).

Certain elements were elevated beyond expected levels, particularly Cr. The lower range of Cr values (below 600 ppm) more clearly demonstrates the internal variety found at Enkomi. However, three samples

(ENK3, ENK43, ENK68) had extremely high values (c. 1200–4000 ppm). Petrographically, ENK3 and ENK68 are clearly of local manufacture but contain an increased number of opaque mineral inclusions, a characteristic also observed by Jones (1986: 343). To confirm this, sample ENK3 was analysed using SEM, revealing numerous examples of

Fig. 15. Biplots: a) K_2O against Na_2O ; and b) alkali sum versus loss on ignition (LOI), showing both negative and positive correlations.

Fig. 16. Results of PCA analysis from hhXRF data. Principal components 1 and 2 together explain 46% of the variance. Components were extracted from the correlation matrix using the dimension reduction factor analysis package in SPSS. Graphs: a) Biplot of PC1 and PC2 by ware; b) PC1/PC2 by fabric group; c) PC1/PC2 by chronology; and, d) PC1/PC2 component plot.

chromite. Therefore, the elevated Cr content is likely the result of the ‘nugget effect’ (Fig. 17a-b), which is further compounded when examining the transition trace elements (TTE: Sc, V, Cr, Co, Cu and Zn). As shown in Fig. 17b, the Cr level of ENK3 is elevated to 4800 ppm, while the hh-XRF measurements for the same sample, show a Cr value of approximately 2200 ppm. Petrographic analysis confirms that ENK3 clearly belongs to the local ‘Enkomi’ group. However, when examined with SEM, numerous opaque minerals in the thin section were identified as chromite, which effectively demonstrated the ‘nugget’ effect.³ TTE values range from 673 to 5790 ppm, driven not only by the high Cr content, but also by elevated Cu levels. All vessels with high TTE values were recovered from copper working contexts in Area III. Outside of

these contexts, the TTE range is more stable, between 673 and 1021 ppm.

With the outliers and problematic elements excluded, the local Enkomi fabrics demonstrate high compositional homogeneity (Table 2), with standard deviations generally lower than one. Biplots of major, minor and trace elements, as well as element ratios, display the challenge of identifying any significant internal variation. To further investigate any meaningful variation, PCA was employed and although some minor chemical groupings emerge, no distinct clusters can be identified that correlate with fabrics, typology, chronological periods, or spatial distribution within the settlement (Fig. 18a–d). Consequently, these groupings are interpreted with caution. They likely reflect natural variations in the raw material exploited by potters rather than differences in source materials or clay recipes, an observation further corroborated by the petrographic analysis.

³ SEM-EDS analysis for this sample is not presented in this paper but is included in Minos’s doctoral thesis (2025).

Table 2

Results of compositional analysis by ICP-OES and ICP-MS for all samples, excluding outliers, with minimum, maximum, and mean values, as well as standard deviations. See Supplementary Material 2 for individual values of samples.

Element	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	STDEV
Major elements (wt.%)				
Al ₂ O ₃	11.7	14.7	13.1	0.6
CaO	11.5	19.8	17.2	2.0
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.71	8.93	8.0	0.5
K ₂ O	0.99	3.09	2.1	0.4
MgO	4.13	6.95	5.5	0.7
MnO	0.179	1.644	1.0	0.4
Na ₂ O	1.32	2.53	1.8	0.3
SiO ₂	49.1	58.6	51.2	1.9
TiO ₂	0.671	0.942	0.8	0.1
Minor and Trace (ppm)				
As	8	78	20.2	14.2
Ba	190	1086	324.3	168.6
Be	0.8	1.5	1.2	0.2
Cd	0.01	0.34	0.2	0.1
Ce	23.8	38.4	29.9	4.2
Co	22	34	28.6	2.9
Cr	252	4858	622.9	826.2
Cs	1.8	4.5	2.8	0.6
Dy	2.85	3.90	3.3	0.3
Er	1.74	2.39	2.1	0.2
Eu	0.777	1.127	0.9	0.1
Gd	2.9	4.2	3.5	0.4
Hf	2.0	4.1	2.5	0.4
Ho	0.60	0.82	0.7	0.1
La	13.1	22.1	16.2	2.2
Lu	0.24	0.36	0.3	0.0
Nb	6.1	10.1	7.8	1.2
Nd	12.0	18.8	14.8	1.8
Ni	116	238	166.0	27.9
Pb	4	38	13.5	6.6
Pr	3.0	4.6	3.7	0.5
Rb	18.3	63.5	43.7	11.5
Sc	16.8	24.5	21.2	1.9
Sm	2.61	3.94	3.2	0.4
Sn	0.8	1.9	1.2	0.3
Sr	389	894	589.8	94.7
Ta	0.40	0.70	0.5	0.1
Tb	0.47	0.64	0.6	0.1
Th	3.3	6.2	4.4	0.7
Tl	0.01	0.21	0.1	0.0
Tm	0.250	0.345	0.3	0.0
U	1.30	5.12	2.1	0.7
V	143	235	181.9	20.5
Y	16.2	22.1	19.2	1.6
Yb	1.70	2.20	1.9	0.2
Zn	73	166	93.2	20.1
Zr	79	180	102.6	19.6

7. Discussion of results: Integration of archaeological, macroscopic, petrographic, and geochemical observations

The integrated study of petrographic, hhXRF, ICP-MS/OES, and SEM-EDS data provided a comprehensive understanding of the ceramic fabrics' mineralogical, chemical, and microstructural properties, offering a baseline for profiling local production techniques at Enkomi during the LCI-II periods. The geological setting of Enkomi, situated in the eastern coast of the island, not far from the Troodos ophiolite, offered a diverse range of raw materials for pottery production, including alluvial clays and calcareous marls from the Nicosia and Athalassa formations. The proximity to the Troodos ophiolite also contributed ophiolitic inclusions and sand temper, which were incorporated into the ceramics. Weathering and fluvial processes likely transported fragments of ophiolitic rocks such as serpentinite and dolerite, along with sand-sized particles, into the surrounding alluvial sediments. Potters may have sourced these naturally occurring inclusions or added sand temper to improve the workability and thermal resistance of their ceramics, a practice that might gradually have become a characteristic of eastern coastal production.

Ceramic petrography revealed three main fabric groups (Groups A, B, and C), with Group A being the most dominant. The subgroups within Group A show minor variations in firing, inclusions, and textural features. This group is considered the local ceramic tradition of Enkomi, representing a continuum with minor changes across different production series and firing techniques. It is characterised by relatively equal but subtly variable proportions of carbonates (microfossils and micritic limestone), chert, ophiolitic inclusions (basalt, dolerite and clinopyroxene), and quartz with a rare but omnipresent set of metamorphic inclusions in a calcareous matrix. There is no distinct pattern linking specific subgroups to particular periods, manufacturing techniques or wares, suggesting that variations in Group A should not be perceived as chronological shifts or particularities of specific ceramic styles or types. Group A is recorded in the majority of selected samples (85% of the total number of samples) and exhibits chemical variation that can be attributed to a number of factors, as discussed further below.

The internal variation in Group A, observed across an increasing number of samples, can be explained by variability in raw material sourcing. Even within a single region, clays, temper, and other inclusions can exhibit significant variation (see A3, as well as A2A/A2B). For example, raw materials from alluvial clays, calcareous marls, and ophiolitic inclusions likely vary in both chemical and mineralogical content. Potters may have accessed different depths or areas of a deposit depending on seasonal availability or environmental conditions, further contributing to variation. It is important to note for example that [Devillers \(2008: 158\)](#) has argued for a large lagoon and potential bay immediately south of Enkomi during the LBA. Additionally, potters may have mixed clays and temper in varying proportions (compare photomicrographs a and b in [Fig. 5](#)) to potentially meet specific production

Fig. 17. Cr/ Ni (ppm) plot with all values (a) and then a lower range of values (b), i.e. below 650 ppm.

Fig. 18. Results of the PCA analysis with ICP-MS and OES data including major elements (Al_2O_3 , CaO , Fe_2O_3 , MgO , MnO , and TiO_2), and minor/trace elements (Ba, Ce, Co, Nb, Nd, Ni, Sr, U, Y, Yb and Zn). The plot accounts for 60.8% of total variance. Principal components were extracted from a correlation matrix using the dimension reduction factor analysis package of SPSS. All the elements' concentrations were log-transformed to base 10. Graphs: a) PC1/PC2 by chronology; b) PC1/PC2 by ware; c) PC1/PC2 by fabric group; and d) PC1/PC2 component plot.

needs, such as enhancing strength, workability, or texture. This can introduce chemical variation even within the same fabric group but is difficult to define geochemically due to the nature of the sample population as described above (e.g., Neff et al., 1989; Sterba et al., 2009). The firing process also plays a role, as variations in temperature, atmosphere, or duration could induce chemical changes in clays, which is best exemplified by comparing the higher fired subgroup A1B and lower fired subgroup A1C.

Several scholars (Tschegg et al., 2009a; Gomez et al., 2002: 33) have argued that Enkomi's clays could have been used without further preparation. However, ethnographic evidence from Cyprus suggests that potters typically mixed clays and tempers, only rarely using raw material without any processing (Hemsley, 1991; Ionas, 2000). The addition of river sand is particularly common in Cyprus, as many local clays, which often contain high levels of montmorillonite (a highly expansive clay mineral), can be excessively plastic (Ionas, 2000: 151; Bear, 1963: 142–144).

Traditional potters in Famagusta mixed three types of clay, including one red clay, sourced from riverbeds south of Enkomi (Ionas, 2000: 154). The variety in the mineral inclusions and the presence of frequent TCFs in Group A is also suggestive of tempering (Quinn, 2022: 230–231). Previous studies of LCIII PWMI at Enkomi (Courtois, 1971) and Iron Age PW from Salamis (Gautier, 1977) also support this long-standing tradition of tempering locally available marls with heterogeneous sand. Jones (1986: 330) even identified one such source as a “Salamian black sand”. This tradition of sandy ‘fabrics’, or fabric recipes, appears to extend from as early as LCIA at Enkomi into the Hellenistic period.

The degree of standardisation within the fabric groupings is a crucial consideration, especially when interpreting petrographic and chemical data. Different potters, production series, or workshops may have employed slightly different practices in sourcing, mixing, or firing materials, leading to chemical diversity within a single group. This variation could also reflect potters' adaptation to the functional needs of different vessel types. For instance, larger, thicker-walled vessels might show more compositional variation compared to smaller, thinner pots

(Rice, 1987: 227, 321; Dikomitou-Eliadou and Kiriati, 2023: 157, Fig.3). Even if no clear pattern emerges linking variations to specific periods or wares, minor shifts in group composition over time could indicate changes in production practices, technological advancements, or shifting stylistic preferences. While compositional analyses may not provide any insight into the organisation of production, as Arnold argued (2000: 369), they could, in this case, represent what he described as a ‘source community’, geographically situated around or very near to Enkomi, but temporally extending over hundreds of years.

The large number of samples analysed in this study, focusing on the early LC periods, makes internal variations more apparent. The analytical techniques employed, such as ceramic thin-section analysis, reveal finer mineral content variations that may not be detectable in smaller sample sets. These microscopic differences, while chemically distinct, may still fall within the same fabric group and offer valuable insight into Enkomi's ceramic production during the LCII-II periods. Furthermore, investigating a single source of pottery production without comparing it to additional sources may result in increased apparent variability, as all samples are considered part of a single compositional “cloud” rather than being constrained by the presence of distinct groups, which could otherwise narrow the range of variation.

Despite variability in elemental composition, the consistency in fabric across the samples encapsulates the character of production at Enkomi. This study comes to reinforce Crewe's (2007a) argument that the fabrics of PW, R/BS, and WPWMI at Enkomi were macroscopically identical with some subtle variation, and likely made from the same or similar raw materials, which was a calcareous marl mixed with rounded alluvial sand (i.e. Group A; see also Crewe, 2007a: 148; Crewe, 2007b: 217; Crewe et al., 2008).

Group A exhibits similarities to later periods as well, such as the PW fabrics from LCIII Enkomi but also Iron Age Salamis (study in progress). Comparisons with other sites, like Alassa, reveal both parallels and contrasts, especially in the use of an analogous calcareous, sand tempered fabric; their “Group A” (Jacobs et al., 2017: 542; Jacobs and Borgers, 2015). At Alassa, petrographic groups of PW, WPWMI, and BS wares show considerable overlap. Likewise, at Enkomi, Group A is used

consistently across periods for different wares, with only Group C showing a ware-specific fabric.

Within the Enkomi sample, Group C represents somewhat distinct pottery making practises compared to Group A and B, involving finer clay preparation; in the case of Group C (both C1A and C1B) particularly associated with the production of PW pithoi. The group's finer texture and combined presence of ophiolitic and sedimentary components suggest the refinement and mixing of clays. LBA pithoi have been often attributed to itinerant potters due to regional variation in fabrics and the need for specialised skills (Keswani, 1989: 18; Pilides, 2000). At Enkomi, subgroup C1A spans LCIA to LCIB, showing no clear chronological separation. Elemental compositions are marginally less calcareous compared to Group A, while the mineral content is not different to that of Group B. There is a consistent presence of specific minerals (e.g., monocristalline quartz, serpentinite, clinopyroxenes, carbonates [micritic limestone]), and chert across Groups suggesting a shared knowledge base for resource selection and processing, drawn potentially from the surrounding environment, which may have been a collective activity tying generations of potters together (Gosselain, 2000: 192). However, the fine to very fine nature of these two fabric groups (B and C) contrasts with the coarser fabrics of the LBA pithoi examined by Nodarou (2017) and Xenophontos et al. (2000). Although Xenophontos et al. (2000: 170–174) did analyse material from Enkomi, only the 'exotics' (their samples 11 and 13) appear to share a similar mineralogical profile and overall fineness to Group C.

In addition to pithoi, other ceramic functional and stylistic classes, such as R/BS jugs and PW bowls and jugs, are also made with the same fabrics. This observation warrants further investigation before assessing the mode of organisation of production associated with the respective petrographic groups and pottery classes. Regarding ceramic fabric fineness, studies of Cypro-Archaic to Hellenistic pottery from Salamis (Gautier, 1977: 8) also identify an 'ultra-fine' fabric, which could correspond to those found in Groups B and C. If these traditions persist along the eastern coast of Cyprus, the higher-fired 'green' fabric (similar to the fabric in subgroup A1B of this study), as described by Courtois (1971) and Gautier (1977), may further support the argument for continuity and persistence in ceramic fabric recipes in the region.

8. Conclusions

This study employed a range of advanced analytical techniques to examine the ceramic fabrics from Enkomi during the LCI-II periods. The findings reveal that Enkomi's local ceramic production, influenced by its proximity to the Troodos ophiolite, used a diverse set of raw materials, including alluvial clays, calcareous marls, and ophiolitic inclusions. These materials were tempered with sand to improve workability and thermal resistance. Petrographic analysis identified three main fabric groups (A, B, and C), with Group A being dominant. This fabric exhibits considerable internal variation due to differences in raw material sourcing, mixing practices, and firing techniques, but no clear link between fabric subgroups and specific periods or wares was found, which suggests perhaps an overall effort to generate a similar clay recipe. The consistency in Group A across different periods suggests a stable local ceramic tradition, though the presence of Groups B and C points to more specialised production practices, particularly in the manufacture of pithoi.

Future work will focus on expanding the analysis to include more comparative studies with other sites on the eastern coast of Cyprus, such as Iron Age Salamis, to investigate the persistence and evolution of these ceramic traditions. Additionally, further research is needed to explore the organisation of production at Enkomi, particularly in relation to the use of specific fabrics across different ceramic classes. Investigating the technological and stylistic continuity of these materials, particularly during the transition to the use of wheel-made pottery, is pivotal in Cypriot ceramic studies. Expanding this study to include a broader range of sites and further refining the petrographic and compositional data

will contribute to a more detailed understanding of the exchange of technical knowledge and raw material sourcing across the region.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chase Alan Mohan Minos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Dikomitou-Eliadou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Elvira Vassilieva:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation. **Patrick Degryse:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary Materials

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2025.105230>.

Data availability

Data is included in the article as supplementary material, and is available upon request.

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